

COMPOSITE LIFE PREDICTION USING A MULTIAXIAL FATIGUE PARAMETER

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ABSTRACT

A generalized strain-life curve has been developed based on a parameter involving the multiaxial alternating shear and normal strains on a critical plane parallel to the fracture plane. This parameter needs only to be related to the experimental data of composite laminae loaded in one direction in order to determine stress-life curves for any other loading direction. The predicted curves are in very good agreement with the experimental data for a glass/epoxy composite.

Keywords: critical plane, multiaxial fatigue parameter, life prediction, glass/epoxy.

1. INTRODUCTION

In polymer based composites, the matrix and fibre-matrix interface are generally weaker than the fibre. Microscopic observations have revealed [1] that fatigue cracks most often initiate and grow within the matrix along a plane parallel to the fibre direction. Therefore it is anticipated that the fatigue process is controlled by the microstresses on these critical planes as well as the properties of the matrix. Also, due to the fibre-matrix interaction a complex stress state occurs in the matrix resulting in a multiaxial stress state on the critical planes. A micromechanical stress analysis is conducted in the present study on glass/epoxy composites to calculate the local stress/strain fields which serve as a basis for determining a multiaxial stress/strain fatigue parameter used to correlate the fatigue life data and to derive a generalized fatigue stress/strain-life curve. This curve is then used to predict the fatigue lives of the composite tested under a variety of loading conditions.

2. CALCULATION OF STRESSES AND STRAINS

It has been shown that ideal periodic packing in unidirectional laminae may be used as a model to successfully predict the elastic, elastoplastic and fracture properties of laminates [2] although the fibre distribution may not be completely uniform. Hence this concept of a repeating unit requires an analysis of only one basic block with one fibre and the adjacent matrix, as shown in Fig. 1. The lamina with the load applied at an angle, α , to the fibres is shown in Figs. 1a, b using the same system of coordinates with the X_3 axis parallel to the fibres, as shown in Fig. 1b. Since each individual fibre is surrounded by other fibres which are symmetrically distributed (Fig. 1c) the stress fields near adjacent fibres must be similar. Therefore, in the case of a uniformly

loaded composite it is sufficient to determine the stress field around only one fibre (Fig. 1d) and because of the four-fold symmetry of the unit block the numerical analysis can be reduced to one quarter of the unit block as shown in Fig. 1e.

Fig.1 Repeating unit block model

- (a) Schematic structure of the unidirectional fibre composite
- (b) Coordinate system used in the microstress analysis
- (c) Symmetry of the periodic composite structure
- (d) Basic block of the composite structure and the coordinate system
- (e) Finite element model of the basic block unit

2.1 Linear Elastic Stress Analysis

The first step in the analysis establishes the relationship between the macrostresses S_{ij} in the lamina and the point to point microstresses σ_{ij} in the matrix and fibre. The macrostresses are usually used as input data in further analysis since they are linearly related to the applied load. Because of the periodic structure, adjacent basic blocks (Fig. 1d) containing one fibre match exactly without any overlapping. Therefore rectangular blocks must remain rectangular under deformation. This constraint allows the basic deformation to be modelled by only five deformation states, namely I, II, III, IV, V as shown in Figure 2. The microstresses for each deformation state can be calculated by finite element analysis, using the quadrant shown in Fig. 1e. Consequently, the corresponding macrostresses can be determined from

$$S_{ij} = \frac{1}{\Omega} \iiint_{\Omega} \sigma_{ij} d\Omega \quad (1)$$

where Ω represents the volume.

The calculations are repeated for each of the deformation modes. The deformation modes I, II and III are associated with macrostresses components S_{11} , S_{22} and S_{33} respectively whereas the only non-zero microstress components which may occur under these deformation states are σ_{11} , σ_{22} , σ_{12} and σ_{33} .

Figure 2. Deformation states and corresponding boundary conditions permissible for the basic block unit

Following Lin et al [2], the relationship between microstresses and macrostresses can be expressed as

$$\begin{bmatrix} \sigma_{11} \\ \sigma_{22} \\ \sigma_{12} \\ \sigma_{33} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} A_{11} & A_{12} & A_{13} \\ A_{21} & A_{22} & A_{23} \\ A_{31} & A_{32} & A_{33} \\ A_{41} & A_{42} & A_{43} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} S_{11} \\ S_{22} \\ S_{33} \end{bmatrix} \quad (2)$$

In the case of deformation states IV and V the associated non-zero macrostress components are S_{13} and S_{23} and the corresponding non-zero microstress components are σ_{13} and σ_{23} . The relation between the macrostresses and microstresses for deformation states IV and V can be written

$$\begin{bmatrix} \sigma_{13} \\ \sigma_{23} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} B_{11} & B_{12} \\ B_{21} & B_{22} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} S_{13} \\ S_{23} \end{bmatrix} \quad (3)$$

The microstresses σ_{ij} or external load can be calculated by using eqns. (2) and (3) provided that parameters A_{ij} and B_{ij} are known.

Finite element analysis based on the quadrant shown in Fig. 1e is carried out once for each deformation state. Superposition of the calculated stress components allows the two corresponding stress tensors S_{ij} and σ_{ij} given in eqns. (2) and (3) to be determined. Thus, knowing the macrostress state S_{ij} and the corresponding microstress state σ_{ij} at each point (X_1, X_2, X_3) of the analyzed quadrant (Fig. 1e) parameters A_{ij} and B_{ij} can be determined from eqns. (2) and (3) respectively. These parameters are calculated for each finite element shown in Fig. 1e. An example of a typical microstress field is shown in Fig. 3. The microstress field was determined for a representative quadrant in a 0.6 volume fraction E-glass fibre reinforced epoxy composite loaded at an angle of 45 degrees to the fibre axis. The relevant material properties are $E_r = 7.2 \times 10^4$ MPa, $E_m = 4.5 \times 10^3$ MPa, $\nu_r = 0.27$, $\nu_m = 0.4$, $\sigma_o = 106$ MPa, $n = 3$, where the last two are the strength coefficient and exponent in the Ramberg-Osgood relation for the epoxy matrix. The distribution of the stress component σ_{11} is shown in Fig. 3a and the distribution of the shear component σ_{13} is represented in Fig. 3b. It is seen that the highest concentrations of both stress components occur adjacent to the fibre where $X_2 \rightarrow 0$.

Due to the stress concentration near the fibre it is anticipated that local plastic yielding may occur and therefore it has also to be considered.

Figure 3. Distribution of microstresses in glass/epoxy composites

- a) normalized normal stress σ_{11}/S_a
- b) normalized shear stress σ_{13}/S_a

2.2 Localized Elastoplastic Stress-Strain Analysis

For the evaluation of the local elastoplastic strains and stresses under static and cyclic loading, approximation formulae are frequently used [3]. The most often employed is that derived by Neuber for an uniaxial stress. The extension to multiaxial stress states has been reported in reference [3] in the form of

$$\varepsilon_{ij} \sigma_{ij} = \sigma_{ij}^e \varepsilon_{ij}^e \quad (i,j = 1,2,3) \quad (4)$$

In order to calculate the local stresses and strains, the constitutive equation for the material must be taken into consideration and this may be accomplished by using the generalized Ramberg-Osgood relation for multiaxial stress states given by:

$$\varepsilon_{ij} = \frac{1+\nu}{E} \sigma_{ij} - \frac{\nu}{E} \sigma_{kk} \delta_{ij} + \frac{3}{2E} D_{ij} \left(\frac{\sigma_{eq}}{\sigma_o} \right)^{n-1} \quad (5)$$

where

$$D_{ij} = \sigma_{ij} - \frac{1}{3} \sigma_{kk} \delta_{ij} \quad (6)$$

and

$$\sigma_{eq} = \left(\frac{3}{2} D_{ij} D_{ij} \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} \quad (7)$$

There is a symmetry about the plane x_1 - x_3 at the point of the highest stress concentration in the matrix (Fig. 3), hence

$$\sigma_{12} = \sigma_{23} = 0 \quad (8)$$

Equation (5) together with the conditions given by Moftakhar and Glinka [3] form a set of eight equations sufficient for determination of all stress and strain components in the presence of localized plasticity in the region of the stress concentration.

Using the stresses and strains, σ_{ij}^e and ε_{ij}^e , given by elastic analysis, the eight required elastoplastic stress/strain components σ_{ij} and ε_{ij} can be determined.

3.0 MULTIAXIAL FATIGUE PARAMETER

One of the fundamental problems in analysing failure due to a multiaxial cyclic stress state is the choice of a parameter which represents the material resistance under a variety of loading conditions. A promising theory [4,5] combining shear and normal strains has been proposed based on the maximum shear strain on the critical (i.e. crack initiation [4]) plane while considering the additional effect of tensile strain [4]:

$$\tilde{\gamma}^* = \tilde{\gamma} + K\tilde{\varepsilon} \quad (9)$$

where K is material constant determined from fatigue test data obtained under different loading conditions. For steel $K=1$ is often chosen [4,5].

The final equation is usually presented in its empirical form:

$$\lg \tilde{\gamma}^* = A + m \lg N_f \quad (10)$$

4.0 EXPERIMENTAL VERIFICATION OF THE MULTIAXIAL FATIGUE PARAMETER FOR GLASS REINFORCED EPOXY

The set of experimental data obtained for the epoxy based composite reinforced with 0.6 volume fraction E-glass fibres was taken from reference [6].

The macrostress-fatigue life results (S_{max} vs. N_f) were obtained using 19mm wide by 1mm thick rectangular specimens with a gauge length of 100mm tested under the stress ratio of $R=0.1$. The fatigue lives N_f were defined as number of cycles to the final failure.

There were six sets of data corresponding to different angles, α , of the load to fibre axis, namely 5° , 10° , 15° , 20° , 30° and 60° . The set of data obtained for the load/fibre angle of 10° was used to derive the generalized multiaxial strain-life relation in the form

$$\lg(\tilde{\gamma}_{13} + K\tilde{\epsilon}_{11}) = A + m\lg(2N_f) \quad (11)$$

The best fit was found for $K=1$, $A=-1.3946$ and $m=-0.100577$. The experimental data and the line for the least squares fit are shown in Fig. 4.

In this case linear elastic and elastic-plastic stress-strain analyses were carried out because the local strains for the low cycle fatigue lives were higher than the yield limit of the epoxy material. Since no cyclic properties were available the monotonic properties were used in the calculations.

Figure 4. Fatigue lives of glass/epoxy composite specimens tested at an angle of 10° to the fibre direction

The relation (11) obtained from the specimens tested under the load to fibre angle of 10° was used to predict the fatigue lives of specimens tested at the angles of 5° , 15° , 20° , 30° , and 60° . The comparison of the predicted and experimental results is shown in Fig. 5. The results indicate that the parameter $(\tilde{\gamma}_{13} + K\tilde{\epsilon}_{11})$ describes well all the experimental data and that the effect of the load/fibre angle can be predicted. It is known that the local strains depend strongly on the load level and the load/fibre angle which affects both the local strain magnitude and the ratio of the shear to normal strain. However, when the data are plotted in the form of the $\lg\tilde{\gamma}^* - \lg N_f$ relation all the experimental results collapse into one master curve as shown in Fig. 6.

Figure 5. Effect of load/fibre angle on the fatigue life of the glass/epoxy composite; comparison of experimental and predicted results

Figure 6. Normalized plot using the multi-axial fatigue parameter $\tilde{\gamma}^*$ for the glass/epoxy composite

5.0 CONCLUSIONS

It has been shown that microstress/strain analysis in conjunction with the multiaxial fatigue parameter can be applied to successfully predict the fatigue lives of long fibre glass/epoxy composites. The multiaxial parameter enables a generalized strain-life relationship to be determined using limited experimental data. Once the generalized relationship is known the life of the composite cycled under any combination of loads and load-fibre angle may be predicted.

The multiaxial fatigue parameter is expressed as a combination of the shear and normal strains on the critical plane parallel to the fibres. In high cycle fatigue, application of the linear elastic analysis gives very satisfactory results. However, in the low cycle regime the local inelastic strains on the critical plane should be determined (in this case using the generalized Neuber rule) and incorporated into the parameter.

The fatigue process of the composites considered in this work was controlled mainly by the local shear strain on the critical plane and the contribution of the normal strain was secondary. By using the multiaxial fatigue parameter very good agreement was achieved between the experimental and predicted lives.

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7.0 REFERENCES

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